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**CWEA: Automated log retrieval for
performance analysis of service-oriented
scientific workflows.**

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Abstract

A complex scientific workflow often consists of many software tools or services, and those components are deployed on distributed infrastructures, e.g., when processing data from distributed sources. The runtime behavior of the workflow, e.g., monitored by the underlying infrastructure, is important for analyzing the provenance of the workflow, in particular when the workflow has unexpected performance issues or failure. However, it is very challenging to analyze the workflow performance, due to the difficulty in gathering and analyzing performance metrics across distributed infrastructures. Moreover, the workflow provenance and the system logs are provided by workflow management system and the underlying infrastructure, and they contain different information. In this thesis we aim to tackle this issue by proposing a tool that can automatically gather performance information (e.g., CPU, Memory and Network) for a given service-oriented workflow. We assume the monitoring of the components and their machines is set up according to a common standard including often used tools like *Docker*, *cAdvisor* and the metric collector *Prometheus*. The proposed tool aims to integrate the different information, and provide methods for visual aid and evaluation of the system performance on different aspects. The prototype uses the provenance format, produced by *Apache Taverna*, which is a widely used workflow management system in different fields of science. We validate our tool by simulating heavy resource load to create peaks in the performance data, and demonstrate how the tool detects and visualizes the irregularities in the experiment.

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1 Introduction

In the past decades, computer technology has become essential for supporting almost every aspect of scientific research. Whereas before the scientific community only distinguished Theoretical and Experimental science, we now have two new paradigms: Data-intensive and Computational science. Computational science refers to studies that aim to simulate complex phenomena using software models. E.g. simulating the 3D impact of an asteroid 10 kilometers in diameter[15]. To accurately model such a complex phenomenon, an immense number of variables have to be taken into account, resulting in resource-heavy computations. Data-intensive science is a new paradigm after computational science, some examples of its application can be found in Climate Research. E.g. to help better understand the consequences of global warming, scientists are looking at a diverse set of data sources obtained from model simulation experiments and remote sensors (such as radar and satellites)[1]. The big challenge of Data-intensive science is locating, storing, moving and processing the petabytes of such data.

In the data-intensive and computational sciences, different software environments are needed for supporting experiments, managing research data, and for using infrastructures like Cloud. Because of the service-oriented nature of these infrastructures, tools and data are often made accessible using web-services. This way, the scientist is given a convenient way of interacting with the needed resources. The instruments and tools hosted in the infrastructure may differ in computational needs, resulting in implementations using different technologies. However, in the context of our study, they can be considered as homogeneous Cloud-based resources using web services as a uniform interface of deployment.

1.1 Gap analysis

Scientific workflows automate the computing tasks of complex scientific experiments, often across different infrastructures. For example, to identify a type of protein, biologists must use algorithms and data hosted on different sites. The scientific workflow acts as the abstraction of logic among the steps that are performed during the experiment. It describes the processes and computations that need to be executed and how they are orchestrated. Scientific workflows can conveniently be stored and published for reuse by other researchers. During the life-cycle of scientific workflows, including design, creation, execution, testing, and publication, we can identify the following key roles:

- **Scientists:** They formulate a hypothesis concerning a scientific problem or specific research purposes. Based on the research question derived from their hypothesis, scientists define a set of processes and analysis methods they want to perform. A typical activity is to model the logic of a scientific application or experiment using a Workflow Management System (WFMS), which manages the execution processes of an application or an experiment.
- **The Virtual Research Environments (VREs):** They are also referred as Virtual Laboratories or Science Gateways. VREs aid users (scientists) in discovering available sources of data and services, and combining them into a workflow using a WFMS.
- **Research Infrastructures (RI):** They are facilities that provide resources and services for scientific communities to conduct research and foster innovation[11]. RIs typically use service-oriented architectures to provide access to instruments and data sets.
- **e-Infrastructures:** They are typically responsible for providing digital services in terms of networking, computing and data management e.g., Cloud infrastructures. In our context, the Clouds act as a central environment for hosting data management services in Research Infrastructures. This is where the performance data is monitored.

Although the boundaries between the functionalities of each role are not always entirely clear, collectively they represent an important trend in many international research and development projects. Figure 1 shows how these abstractions relate, and how the user interacts with different components within them. For instance, the web-services provided by a RI are often deployed on Cloud environments provided by e-Infrastructures.

Figure 1: This diagram shows an abstract model of the components inside an eScience environment in which scientific workflows are composed and executed.

Workflow Management Systems are used by scientists for the creation, execution and publication of scientific workflows. These systems use a convenient GUI and straight-forward functionality to quickly build workflows comprising various steps. Currently, many VRE's provide users with a WFMS that is accessible online to integrate functions like automated publishing.

Provenance is often used by WFMS's to log the execution of a workflow, including start and end timestamps for all of the steps that were performed. Provenance is information about entities, activities, and people involved in producing a piece of data or thing, which can be used to form assessments about its quality, reliability or trustworthiness[22]. This makes provenance a fitting scheme for describing the execution of a workflow. In the context of virtual data/entities, provenance models are often stored in the RDF format, a widely used W3C standard[21] with many tools available to parse and query files of its type.

Nowadays, scientific workflows are often orchestrated and executed in Cloud environments. In this context, an important task for scientists is to analyze the data flow and the logs of the workflow processes for reproducing the workflow execution, namely workflow provenance. The provenance information only allows scientists to optimize the workflow at the high application level, e.g., workflow flow logic, input/output of workflow processes, and data that can be gathered from storage. However, the optimization on the workflow performance requires sufficient information on run-time monitoring on underlying infrastructure, and the effective linking between high level workflow provenance information and the low level system monitoring logs. Currently, little effort to automate this process has been made. Gathering the time-relevant data needed for analysis requires knowledge on the tools and architectures used for low-level system monitoring of the performance metrics. Since there is not yet an automated way of doing this, it is a difficult task that requires a considerable amount of manual effort.

1.2 Research Problem

We define the following problem:

The gap between high-level workflow execution and low-level resource metrics makes it difficult to discover anomalies that could affect the execution performance of scientific workflows.

In this thesis, we aim to bridge the gap by proposing an effective tool that:

1. automates the gathering of contextual performance data based on a given workflow.
2. visualizes the performance data found.

3. provides aid for detecting anomalies in resource utilization and improving workflow execution.

In the next sections we will discuss the research questions that arise with this problem. For each question we present a hypothetical solution. We will implement the hypotheses and test them to evaluate their validity.

1.2.1 Research Question 1

R1: *How can we effectively detect low-level performance anomalies resulting from high-level workflow execution in research infrastructures?*

H1: *Using workflow provenance to automatically collect relevant performance data, we can simplify the process of finding anomalies or bottlenecks in a workflow execution.*

Subquestions:

- 1.1 *What relevant data can we retrieve from workflow provenance?*

Provenance of a workflow contains many of its execution properties. To find which of these properties are useful for our research, we have to inspect the contents of provenance files.

- 1.2 *How can we retrieve the needed performance logs?*

There are multiple monitoring architectures available used both in scientific and enterprise infrastructures. We will have to examine possible ways to access the performance data that was gathered by these monitoring services.

- 1.3 *To what extent can we automate this process?*

To minimize user/controller interaction and improve the usability of our solution we have to investigate the extent to which the functionality of our system can be automated without the need for input.

1.2.2 Research Question 2

R2: *How can we provide insight and recommendations based on the performance data that is found?*

H2: *By analyzing performance data, we can make recommendations to help improve workflow execution performance in the future.*

Subquestions:

- 2.1 *How can we detect parts of the workflow in need of improvement?*

To recommend improvements to the user we have to explore algorithms that can be used for anomaly detection in timeseries performance data.

- 2.2 *How will the findings be delivered?*

Assuming a user is going to use our solution system we have to present the findings intuitively. However, we also have to consider presenting the findings to automated controllers.

1.3 Contribution

In our literature study, we were unable to find an approach for bridging workflow execution and performance analysis that is not dependent on a specific infrastructure implementation and semantically links distributed logs. This gives us the chance to investigate this branch in the study of workflows and distributed system monitoring, possibly leading to studies introducing better frameworks and improvements upon the prototypes we discuss in our work.

Apart from the tool we are going to implement, we also touch upon a more abstract aspect of this topic, namely an architecture that could be implemented as a standard to improve the interchangeability of tools used for the monitoring of domain-specific systems. The architecture can be used as a foundation to build a common standard that can be implemented in various research infrastructures. The implementation of such a standard will support future implementations and improvements in correlating workflow events with system performance.

Our proposed architecture would greatly benefit different users that interact with research infrastructures. Developers and researchers working with scientific instruments hosted in these environments would be able to estimate the resource usage and evaluate the performance of their tool in different contexts with more ease. Furthermore, data engineers working on the creation and maintenance of the research infrastructures would be able to detect and fix bottlenecks in certain system components more easily.

1.4 Outline

In the upcoming sections, we will discuss this research topic in more depth. We will start by addressing the background and related work on this topic. Next, we discuss the architecture we designed to create the solution presented in this work. Here we will illustrate how the application was designed and implemented, clarifying which tools and techniques were used in the process. Following up, we describe the experimental setup, in which we demonstrate and test our application on simulations of heavy resource usage. We then analyze and evaluate the results that were gathered in these tests. The last section presents a conclusion and future studies and improvements relevant to our topic.

2 Background and Related work

In recent years, there has been a notable increase in studies that focus on the improvement of large-scale research infrastructures. The topics discussed in these studies include scientific workflows, resource monitoring and data provenance. We will discuss some of the relevant topics and present a number of related papers.

2.1 State of the art

2.1.1 Research Infrastructures

With the increase in scientific data, it becomes a challenge for researchers to store and share resources efficiently. The large amount of data, paired with the algorithms used to analyze it, leads to increasing demand for computing storage and network resources. It is therefore clear that there is a need for:

1. information retrieval from many distributed data sources.
2. access and control to remote computing resources and experimental equipment.

As a result, e-Science has emerged. This new discipline utilizes computer technology for the undertaking of modern scientific investigation, including preparation, experimentation, data collection, result dissemination, and long-term storage and accessibility of all materials generated through the scientific process[4].

The notion of e-Science has been realized by infrastructures that aim to connect many distributed resources. These infrastructures often comprise of many different components and consist of multiple abstraction layers to allow scalability[8]. The availability of resources helps support the execution of Scientific workflows that need data and resources computing in different contexts. With the use of web services as building blocks, numerous data sources and computational instruments have been made available by researchers for other researchers to use[17]. The implementation of these features led to the creation of the Cyberinfrastructure (United States) and e-Infrastructure (Europe), currently the prominent environments used for scientific collaboration.

2.1.2 Scientific Workflows

Service-oriented architecture has become a popular paradigm for creating software composed of loosely coupled, distributed services. Complex systems can comprise of many of these services, exposing a large variety of functionalities. Often, these services have to work together to fulfill a specific task or goal. The coordination needed for this is achieved through the use of workflow technologies. Workflows act as a glue, connecting distributed and often separately hosted web services.

Once the e-Science infrastructures scaled up and became more distributed in nature, there came a need for scientific workflows. Since these infrastructures consist of many distributed services, workflows provide an easy way for scientists to combine functionalities to reach a certain goal. Not only do they support the automation of repetitive tasks, but they can also capture complex analysis processes at various levels of detail and systematically capture provenance information for the derived data products [14]. Currently, scientific workflows are frequently used by researchers of different domains to be able to obtain, analyze and process data from services hosted all over the world. These workflows can easily be built and executed using many available tools and can be shared among researchers of different institutes.

Workflows also have an application in the business community, namely the automation of a business process describing a process in which documents, information or tasks are passed from one participant (human or machine) to another[18].

2.1.3 Distributed system monitoring

The implementation of DevOps practices in many software projects enforces the need for continuous monitoring of the systems they have in use[2]. With the increasing adoption of service-oriented

architectures, the systems in need of monitoring have become larger in scale, often comprising components that are hosted on different machines and infrastructures. Monitoring and analyzing the metrics of systems that consist of many distributed components has proven to be a challenge, leading to a substantial amount of research in recent years. With this research came a high number of new tools and architectures used for simplifying data monitoring. Many tools and technologies we use in our research are heavily used for the deployment of enterprise-scale software projects. Currently, many businesses choose to acquire ready-to-go infrastructures from cloud service enterprises. In many of these cases, the monitoring functionality is made available by the cloud providers. This makes the process of gathering metrics easier, with administrators only needing to integrate them.

One of the common concepts used for the deployment of systems comprising many distributed services is containerization. A container is a lightweight, isolated operating system running inside the host system[10]. A container can run an application, or execute specific tasks, making it highly convenient for DevOps related tasks. Docker is one of the most popular tools used for creation, orchestration and deployment of such containers. Popular examples include Kubernetes[20] and Docker Swarm[9], tools that provide an interface for automating deployment, scaling, and managing containerized applications. Monitoring technologies have adapted to these new technologies, resulting in specific tools for measuring and recording performance metrics inside clusters of containers.

2.1.4 Provenance

Provenance (also known as the audit trail, lineage, and pedigree) of data contains information about the process and data used for its derivation[7]. It contains information about entities, activities, and people involved in producing a piece of data or thing, which can be used to form assessments about its quality, reliability or trustworthiness[16]. Currently, there are many challenges concerning the recording and implication of provenance in large scale cloud infrastructures. Provenance data has many implications like in fraud detection, debugging and analysis of infrastructure-level workflow performance.

The PROV data format is one of the standards recommended by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) and is often used to define data on which changes have been made. Scientific workflows can consist of multiple steps, where one process can output data that is used as input in the next. This process involves entities and activities that can be described using PROV to form an easily traceable sequence. Since it is one of the recommended standards of W3C, many tools for modeling and querying PROV exist.

2.2 Related work

2.2.1 A Provenance-based Adaptive Scheduling Heuristic for Parallel Scientific Workflows in Clouds.

In this study, Oliveira et al. propose a solution to challenges such as scheduling workflow activities in large-scale e-Science infrastructure[26]. To do this, they introduce an adaptive scheduling heuristic for parallel execution of scientific workflows in the cloud that is based on a number of criteria. Their approach also scales resources up and down according to predefined restrictions defined by the scientists and a tuning based on provenance data captured and queried at run-time. The solution discussed in this paper proposes a tool that improves cloud performance using workflow provenance data. The provenance data is queried and retrieved at runtime, and then directly used to make automated decisions on how to scale machines on the cloud infrastructure to improve performance. While this study has a similar goal as ours, namely improving infrastructure performance based on provenance data, they do not use provenance to retrieve resource usage. In their case, provenance is used to recognize points at which a scaling operation is needed. This operation is then automatically executed without any user interaction.

2.2.2 Provenance in the Cloud: Why and How?

In this study, Imran et al. give an overview of the implications and challenges of provenance data in cloud environments[19]. They start by distinguishing cloud from other infrastructures like Grid, explaining the service-oriented nature of the cloud environment. They discuss the many benefits of a Provenance Enabled Cloud and how it can be used to improve the system. One of the categories discussed here is the detection of patterns: The use of provenance data to find patterns in the Cloud resources usage. These patterns can be further utilized to forecast a future request. This paper contains a lot of valuable information for this thesis. The paper gives a good overview of the current state of provenance data in the cloud and discusses many aspects relevant to our thesis. Furthermore, the part about detecting patterns discusses features that we also try to implement in our thesis.

2.2.3 Provenance for the Cloud

In this work, Muniswamy-Reddy et al. make the case that provenance is crucial for data stored on the cloud and identify the properties of provenance that enable its utility[24]. They continue to examine current cloud offerings and propose three protocols for maintaining data/provenance in current cloud stores. One of the use cases identified in this paper that was particularly relevant for this thesis includes the debugging of experimental result.

This paper discusses among other things a use case that is similar to the one described in our thesis. In the section about the debugging of experimental results they discuss the use of provenance data to retrieve and analyze faults and irregularities in the resource usage. While they did not discuss this in depth, or provide any technical information it was still very useful for categorizing our problem among the many others in this field.

2.2.4 A dashboard for microservice monitoring and management

Mayer et al. implemented a dashboard for microservice monitoring and management [23]. The dashboard allows interactive adaption for different stakeholders needs. Based on interviews held with experienced developers and architects in the field, they were able to round up a list of 5 essential features the dashboard should realize. One of these was the monitoring of performance metrics. Additionally, it allows the user to manually add data-sources that can be gathered from a specific microservice.

In this thesis, we aim to solve a problem similar to the one described by Mayer et al. However, in our research we include the concept of Scientific Workflows interacting with the microservices. This increases the number of possibilities for automating the process of metric gathering.

2.2.5 Overhead Analysis of Scientific Workflows in Grid Environments

Prodan et al. propose an approach that aims to aid workflow end-users and middleware developers to understand the sources of performance losses when executing scientific workflows in grid environments[27]. To achieve this, they propose a model for estimating the ideal lowest execution time of a workflow before expressing the total overhead as the difference between the measured execution time and the ideal time. This work is focused on Grid environments and depends on the presence of a specific scheduler named GRAM[12] to collect the state of each workflow task submitted to a grid site. Moreover, in Grid environments, the performance of the node that is assigned to execute a workflow task is more or less stable.

The problem discussed here is similar to the one we describe in our thesis. We too wish to help application developers inspect causes for bottlenecks more easily. However, this study focuses on the application in Grid environments, while we aim to provide a solution that is infrastructure independent.

2.2.6 Anomaly detection for scientific workflow applications on networked clouds

Here, Gaikwad et al. set up an online mechanism for detecting anomalies while executing scientific workflows on networked clouds[13]. The authors use an integrated framework to collect online

monitoring time-series data from workflow tasks and the infrastructure. This approach is tightly coupled with the Pegasus WFMS which depends on specific worker nodes to execute workflows tasks.

In this study, there is a high focus on detecting anomalies inside scientific cloud infrastructures. In their work, they combine several statistical anomaly detection algorithms to achieve this. This work does not address our problem of how to efficiently gather the needed metrics. Instead, it focuses on anomaly detection algorithms that can produce useful output based on the gathered metrics.

2.2.7 Measuring docker performance: What a mess

Casalicchio et al. explore tools that can be used to monitor the performance of containers[6]. Different tools and methods available were tested and evaluated to make an overview of their uses, advantages and disadvantages. One of the tools discussed is *cAdvisor*. This tool is widely used and was shown to be a consistent instrument for retrieving performance metrics of specific docker containers. The research is useful for any study in which aggregation of resource usage data is a theme. We used its insights to make choices on the technologies to use for our prototype. However, the focus of this thesis is the retrieval of resource data on a more abstract level, including scientific workflows for more contextual information.

2.3 Summary

From our literature study we can conclude that there is a shortage in research concerning the process of collecting performance data based on scientific workflow definitions. From reading the related articles, we identified two main weak points:

- **Focus on Anomaly Detection.** While there are many researches that focus on implementing complex anomaly detection algorithms on performance data, there are a few that discuss possible improvements for the process of contextually gathering this data.
- **Platform dependence.** The few studies we were able to find were either outdated or focused on specific cloud infrastructures, e.g. Grid environments. As a result, the outcomes of these studies are not fully applicable for modern day research environments, in which large-scale infrastructures can be broken down into numerous segregated web services

3 Cross-context workflow execution analyzer (CWEA)

In this section we propose our solution architecture named the **Cross-context workflow execution analyzer (CWEA)**.

3.1 Requirement Analysis

To make our solution functional, we first set some requirements:

1. **Scalability**

The system should be able to scale up to complex workflows consisting of many web-services. Scientific workflows vary in complexity and can often comprise a large number of steps in which calls are made to various distributed services. This emphasizes the need for our system to be able to scale up to support both simple and complex workflows.

2. **Evolvability**

The system should encourage modification for support of new features. Since numerous different data formats, monitoring technologies and data analysis methods exist in modern research environments, we have to assure our system can be easily modified for the support of any particular ones.

3. **Interoperability**

The system should aim at delivering its findings to both users and automated controllers. The findings delivered by our system can be of interest for users seeking to gather insights on the performance data relevant to a workflow. However, the findings can also be useful for self-improving infrastructures that aim to automatically make amends to increase system performance.

4. **Usability**

The system should deliver its output in an intuitive and comprehensible manner. To make the findings understandable for the user we have to make sure the output is presented in a manner that will be easy to interpret.

3.2 Proposed Architecture

In order to meet the requirements mentioned in Section 3.1, we propose an architecture that gathers performance data from heterogeneous and distributed resources. In the design of our solution prototype, we took into account the latest technologies used in DevOps, focusing on performance monitoring and continuous development.

First, we discuss the environment in which our system resides. In this more abstract view, the solution system will be considered a black box. This will make the interactions between the various components that are involved clear, without diving into the details of how the solution system works. Next, we will focus solely on the solution system and discuss the inner architecture and methods we used to design it.

3.2.1 Architecture Environment

Figure 2 shows a high-level view of the interaction between components in our system. First, the user creates or imports a workflow using the WFMS. Next, the workflow is executed by the WFMS, connecting to services hosted on different machines in the process. Once this is finished, the workflow description and provenance files are exported by the user. These files contain endpoints and execution timestamps that can be used to gather performance data and will act as input for the CWEA. The CWEA parses these files and connects to the endpoints to retrieve the necessary performance data. This data is then presented to the user in an interactive GUI. The steps in this process can be seen in Figure 3.

The actor shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3 does not have to be a person. Our system provides the same functionality for automated controllers. In the future, this could allow automated log and data retrieval after a WFMS has executed a certain workflow.

Figure 2: Architecture diagram depicting the interaction between the relevant components.

Figure 3: Sequence diagram depicting the communication between components in the common use case. For simplicity we assume the presence of two hosts.

3.2.2 Internal Architecture

The CWEA enables workflow developers and domain scientists to efficiently view workflow execution data and its corresponding performance metrics in one place. Furthermore, it allows the application of different methods to help analyze and diagnose system performance based on the gathered information. To achieve this functionality, we propose an architecture comprising the following components:

1. **Workflow context data retriever (WCDR):** The WCDR queries the RDF provenance data generated by the WFMS to extract the name, start-time and end-time of each web service call that was made in the workflow. The WCDR also parses the workflow itself to extract the endpoints of the web services used and the type of call made (e.g., GET, POST, etc.).
2. **Resource context data retriever (RCDR):** The RCDR uses the service endpoints ob-

tained by the WCDR to query the corresponding hosts and retrieve available performance data within the web services call time-ranges. This can include a wide range of system data, but for our prototype we focussed on CPU, Memory and Network load.

3. **Workflow execution analyzer (WFEA):** the WFEA abstracts a set of diagnostic algorithms that takes as input the data retrieved by the WCDR and RCDR. It uses this data to analyze performance and correlate events in the resource usage to executions in the workflow. For our current prototype, the WFEA uses a simple algorithm that identifies the most time-consuming steps in the workflow execution. The findings of the WFEA are presented to the user in the interactive GUI, or can be consumed automatically by components such as infrastructure-scale controllers.
4. **Interactive GUI:** this is a web-based interface for the user to select specific hosts and analyze the performance metrics that were retrieved from it.

The diagram in Figure 4 shows how these components interact. To encourage modification of the CWEA for the support of different technologies and data formats, we designed the system using the microservice architecture. To implement this we containerize all of the components, each representing a RESTful microservice with its own functionality. The components communicate using HTTP requests, with JSON as the agreed data format.

The GUI component is the only component that is accessible from the outside. Besides acting as a graphical interface for the user, the back-end of the GUI component is a REST API for automated calls made by other applications. This design assures both manual and automated interaction. For our prototype, the provenance data and workflow are extracted by the user and manually uploaded to the GUI. However, our design will also make it possible to connect to provenance data workflow repositories.

Figure 4: This component diagram shows the microservices forming the CWEA.

To visualize and analyze performance data resulting from the execution of a workflow we describe the following use case:

1. Once the WFMS, in our prototype Taverna is used, has executed a workflow the user exports the workflow data. This includes:
 - XML file containing the workflow description. This includes labels and endpoints of specific processors in the workflow. The information in this file is separate from the workflow execution.
 - Provenance data in RDF format. This contains information on the execution of the workflow, including time-stamps and response messages.

2. The user uploads the provenance and workflow files to the GUI
3. The GUI sends the files to the WCDR where it parses the file and returns for each service in the workflow:
 - Name (e.g. "Get genes")
 - Endpoint (e.g. "http://soap.genome.jp/")
 - Invocation start-time
 - Invocation end-time.

This information is returned in the form of a list and visualized by the GUI. This list can be filtered to select the hosts the user wishes to further analyze.

4. The user specifies the hosts to be analyzed and sends a request to the RCDR via the GUI to gather the relevant performance data. The RCDR attempts to query to databases on the endpoints to retrieve the performance data bound by the time-stamps of each web service invocation.
5. Once the performance data is available to the WFEA, it performs its analysis and returns the results to the GUI.

The sequence diagram in Figure 5 shows the use case described above in more detail.

Figure 5: A detailed sequence diagram, showing the interactions between components and users of the CWEA.

4 System Validation

For this thesis, we implemented a prototype that supports the main functionalities discussed in the architecture section. This includes the following:

- Web-based user interface (GUI)
- Parsing of .prov and .t2flow files exported from Apache Taverna. (WCDR)
- Connecting to host machines involved in the workflow execution. (RCDR)
- Display relevant performance data including CPU, Memory and Network.

4.1 Prototype implementation

Our prototype supports the main use case of the CWEA (shown in Figure 5) in a web-based application. To do this, we implemented the following components:

- **WCDR:** We implemented the WCDR in Java, using the Spring framework to create a RESTful API. It accepts workflow definitions and provenance, returning a list of all web-services that are identified in this data. We used the Apache Jena library to parse and query the provenance data. The workflow definition is parsed separately using the javax XML library.
- **RCDR:** The RCDR is implemented using Node.js and Express to create a RESTful API. It takes as input an endpoint URL and a time interval. Based on these arguments it attempts to connect to the host and retrieve all performance metrics in the specific range. The data is retrieved by making HTTP requests to the database service residing on the host. This way we could easily retrieve metrics for demonstration, without setting up an explicit database connection.
- **GUI** The GUI is a simple web-page written using HTML, CSS and Javascript. It is hosted on the server created by the Spring Framework for the WCDR. The GUI uses basic forms for uploading workflow data and uses the Google Timeline and Dygraphs libraries to present the results to the user.
- **WFEA** For our prototype we did not implement any complicated algorithms for the WFEA. Since it is not the focus of this thesis, we only implemented some simple analysis functions that could be used for the demonstration, including the highlighting and filtering of specific tasks. To reduce the effort for implementation, we added these functions on the front-end as part of the GUI.

The components that comprise the CWEA prototype are deployed as separate Docker containers. Using Docker-compose files we created a deployable cluster of the containers forming the CWEA. In its configuration, we made sure that the containers can easily communicate by labeling their endpoints. The GUI is the only container that can be accessed from outside the cluster environment, allowing us to demonstrate the web-based interface.

All the code discussed in this section can be found on: https://github.com/QC-API-DRIP/eVRE-ENVRI/tree/elias_branch/LOG2PROV. This repository also contains a Docker-compose file that can be used to launch and interact with the CWEA prototype.

4.2 Validation plan

To test our prototype, we set up an experiment which consists of the following steps:

1. We set up web services on various VMs that will act as our hosts. We create a web service that has different functionalities to simulate contrasting types of behavior in resource usage.
2. We use Taverna to create and execute a workflow that makes calls to these web services. Once this is finished, we will be able to obtain a provenance file, accompanied by an XML file in which all the data on the workflow is stored.

3. We will feed these files to our prototype and extract all data needed to access the performance logs of the systems. Once the necessary logs are retrieved, we present them to the user, together with methods to make sense of the data.
4. Finally, we evaluate the ability of the tool to collect and help correlate data from the workflow and performance logs.

4.3 Test bed

During the execution of scientific workflows, processors can make requests to services running on different hosts, as can be seen in Figure 1. The host needs to have a web service and monitoring DB running so the CWEA can access its performance metrics. To make this possible, we deploy the needed components as separate containers using Docker. For our experiment, we deployed the following components:

- **Web service:** This is the RESTful service that is running on the host. Processors in the workflow make requests to this service and the service responds.
- **cAdvisor:** A daemon that collects, aggregates, processes, and exports information about running containers[5]. This includes the performance metrics we are interested in.
- **Prometheus:** A monitoring system that is adopted by many companies and organizations[28]. It is used to scrape the performance metrics from cAdvisor and store it as timeseries data. This data can then be queried and retrieved when needed over an HTTP connection.

Figure 6: This diagram depicts the architecture of the host running the necessary containers.

The containers described are clustered using the Docker `Swarm` functionality. This turns the group of isolated containers into a single virtual Docker engine, making it easier to establish connections between different running containers. Using this architecture, we can set different containers to be accessible on different ports when connecting to the host. Note that not all of the containers need to be accessible from outside this engine. For instance, since there is no need for the cAdvisor container to be accessed from any component outside the host, we keep it isolated. In Figure 6 this set-up is shown in more detail.

The triangles in Figure 6 represent the ports for external connection. As can be seen in the diagram, cAdvisor is responsible for gathering the performance metrics from all the running containers. This makes the Prometheus container dependent on the presence of cAdvisor, as it would else have no data to store.

For our tests, we set up this architecture on three separate VMs that will act as our hosts. In the results and figures, these will be labeled A, B and C. In the table below the exact specifications of these VMs are listed. Our goal in this research is to see how we can gather logs from an environment with separate hosts. For this reason, we did not choose to cluster the VMs. The simple setup used

in our experiment is not typical for scientific infrastructures, but we believe it is representative for our work since the aspects of our interest remain the same in scenarios with more VMs and more complex services.

Operating System	Debian GNU/Linux 9 (stretch)
Kernel	Linux 4.9.0-8-amd64
Architecture	x86-64
CPU-version	Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2690 0 @ 2.90GHz
CPU-cores	1
Cache-size	20480 KB
Virtual Memory	4 GB

4.4 Test web service

For our experiment we made a simple RESTful API that allows various operations. The API is based on a simple `Node.js` image processing web service and can perform effects like greyscale, color-invert and fading when given an input image. We modified this API to mimic heavy resource usage on the host machine. To accomplish this we implemented the following calls:

Type	Path	Description
GET	<code>"/lightweight"</code>	A lightweight operation that returns some data.
POST	<code>"/CPU_intensive"</code>	A CPU intensive operation that exhausts the available CPU cores.
POST	<code>"/MEM_intensive"</code>	A Memory intensive operation that exhausts available virtual memory.
POST	<code>"/custom"</code>	An operation that takes as input a custom Linux command to be executed.

We used the `stress-ng` Linux package[29] to implement the intensive operations. This command-line tool is often used for benchmarking and allows the exhaustion of various system resources. In our case, we used the following commands:

- `'stress-ng --cpu 1 --cpu-method ackermann -t 15s'`: This command starts 1 stressor that uses the Ackermann function to exhaust CPU cores. The Ackermann function is a highly recursive function[30] that is often used for testing and benchmarking purposes. This command is set to exhaust the CPU for 15 seconds.
- `'stress-ng --vm 6 --vm-method ror -t 15s'`: This command starts 6 stressors that will exhaust the virtual memory of the host machine using the `ror` algorithm. This algorithm fills memory with a random pattern and then sequentially rotates 64 bits of memory right by one bit. This command is set to exhaust memory for 15 seconds.

The `/custom` path can take as input any Linux command (e.g. `stress-ng` calls) and execute them. This way, we were able to experiment with various exhaustion methods and dynamically create many resource-specific operations.

The operations discussed above are built underneath the basic functionality of the image processing API. For instance, the `CPU-intensive` operation takes as input an image and returns a grey-scaled version of the image. Since these operations take input data and return an output of the same type, we were able to chain operations in the workflow and simulate real scenarios easily. Since the image effects we selected execute fast and are extremely low on resource usage compared to the intensive operations, they can be neglected in the results.

All the code discussed in this section can be found on: <https://github.com/eliasKA/simplewebservice1>

4.5 Test workflow

To construct and execute the workflow to perform our experiments we used the Taverna WFMS. In this workflow, we made calls to the web service and designed both sequential and parallel executions. An example of such a workflow is given in Figure 7. For the structure of the workflows, we examined published scientific workflows of different domains[25] and tried to make some resembling examples. We chose to implement both sequential and parallel executions in the workflow to replicate realistic scenarios

Once the workflows are executed, Taverna allows the export of all execution logs. This includes the following files of our interest:

- `workflow.t2flow`: An XML file containing the description of the workflow itself. It does not contain any information on the execution, it only defines the structure and characteristics of the workflow model.
- `prov.ttl`: A file containing all the provenance execution data of the workflow. It is stored in the Terse RDF Triple Language (`.ttl`) format which is a W3C syntax for expressing data in the RDF data model[3].

Figure 7: A simple workflow made of six tasks spread over VMs A, B and C.

5 Results

To obtain the results shown in this section, we have executed the sample workflow described in section 4.5. This workflow makes calls to the test webservice, which are hosted on three separated VMs/ Once executed, we export the workflow description and provenance and provide them as input for the CWEA prototype using the GUI. We present a demonstration of the use case presented in 3.2.2. From a users perspective, this comprises the following steps:

1. The user opens the web-application and is presented with the GUI.

2. The user uploads the input files, this includes:

- (a) the workflow description (.t2flow)
- (b) the workflow provenance (.ttl)

3. The CWEA parses the files and extracts the steps performed in the workflow. The user is presented with an interface for analysis of the workflow execution. This includes the following:

- (a) Execution analysis list: a table containing all the tasks that were completed during workflow execution, accompanied by their properties. For each of the tasks, the name, endpoint, HTTP method and time-range are mentioned.

Output

<input type="checkbox"/>	Name	Endpoint	Method	Start-time	End-time
<input type="checkbox"/>	GETIMAGE	http://cori.lab130.uvalight.net:8080	GET	2019-2-29 21:45:5.614	2019-2-29 21:45:5.801
<input type="checkbox"/>	cpu1	http://jang.lab130.uvalight.net:8080/exhaustCPU	POST	2019-2-29 21:45:5.819	2019-2-29 21:45:28.648
<input type="checkbox"/>	cpu2	http://cori.lab130.uvalight.net:8080/exhaustCPU	POST	2019-2-29 21:45:28.666	2019-2-29 21:45:49.775
<input type="checkbox"/>	cpu3	http://bose.lab130.uvalight.net:8080/exhaustCPU	POST	2019-2-29 21:45:49.791	2019-2-29 21:46:11.591
<input type="checkbox"/>	mem1	http://jang.lab130.uvalight.net:8080/exhaustMEM	POST	2019-2-29 21:45:49.811	2019-2-29 21:46:15.851
<input type="checkbox"/>	mem2	http://cori.lab130.uvalight.net:8080/exhaustMEM	POST	2019-2-29 21:46:11.605	2019-2-29 21:46:36.178

Visualize data

The user can select/unselect items in the table to filter the results.

Output

<input type="checkbox"/>	Name	Endpoint	Method	Start-time	End-time
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GETIMAGE	http://cori.lab130.uvalight.net:8080	GET	2019-2-29 21:45:5.614	2019-2-29 21:45:5.801
<input type="checkbox"/>	cpu1	http://jang.lab130.uvalight.net:8080/exhaustCPU	POST	2019-2-29 21:45:5.819	2019-2-29 21:45:28.648
<input type="checkbox"/>	cpu2	http://cori.lab130.uvalight.net:8080/exhaustCPU	POST	2019-2-29 21:45:28.666	2019-2-29 21:45:49.775
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	cpu3	http://bose.lab130.uvalight.net:8080/exhaustCPU	POST	2019-2-29 21:45:49.791	2019-2-29 21:46:11.591
<input type="checkbox"/>	mem1	http://jang.lab130.uvalight.net:8080/exhaustMEM	POST	2019-2-29 21:45:49.811	2019-2-29 21:46:15.851
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	mem2	http://cori.lab130.uvalight.net:8080/exhaustMEM	POST	2019-2-29 21:46:11.605	2019-2-29 21:46:36.178

Visualize data

(b) Execution timeline: based on the execution analysis list, this visualization provides to the user an overview of the time taken to execute each task.

The tasks are shown in different colors according to the associated service host. The timeline also provides more details on the execution duration of a task once a specific bar is selected.

4. The CWEA retrieves the relevant performance data and plots them in graphs. The y-axis shows the resource usage while the x-axis depicts the time of the recorded value. Furthermore, the lines in the graphs represent different hosts, matching the colors used in the execution timeline. For our prototype, we support output for four resources:

(a) CPU: This graph shows the CPU resources utilized by each service during the workflow.

(b) Memory: This graph shows the memory resources utilized by each service during the workflow execution.

(c) Network in: This graph shows the incoming data for each task, execution.

(d) Network out: This graph shows the outgoing data for each task, execution.

5. The graphs that are presented to the user are interactive and allow:

- (a) Zooming in/out on specific sections.
- (b) Highlighting the sections in the graph that are associated with certain steps in the workflow.

6 Discussion

The CWEA tool eases the process of gathering relevant performance data by automating the process of log retrieval. Manually, this would require users to connect to all individual hosts and access the relevant databases. Furthermore, the user would then need to query or filter the data for the specific time-ranges in the workflow. Even when all of this is done, the user would not have a clarifying overview of what happened on each host throughout the workflow execution, especially as the number of hosts increases.

The CWEA prototype we implemented only supported some of the very basic functionalities. However, with it we were able to show the increase in efficiency and clarity that results from a solution for automated gathering and analyzing of performance data based on workflow provenance. With the prototype, the user is presented with all relevant performance metrics in a few simple steps. The results are displayed in an intuitive manner using lists, timelines and graphs. The user can browse and go through specific parts of the results and focus on regions of interest. With the consistent use of colors in both the timeline and graphs, the user can quickly relate parts of the graph to steps taken in the workflow using the highlighting functionality. By combining the data of individual hosts into a single graph, the user is given a clarifying overview of the performance data during the workflow.

6.1 Reflection

Based on the architecture design and system validation, we were able to prove the hypotheses mentioned in 1.2 and answer all relevant questions.

6.1.1 Research Question 1

R1: *How can we effectively detect low-level performance anomalies resulting from high-level workflow execution in research infrastructures?*

H1: *Using workflow provenance to automatically aggregate relevant performance data we can improve the ease of finding anomalies resulting from workflow execution.*

By implementing a prototype that supports the main functionality of our solution architecture, we were able to show that our tool hugely improves the process of gathering performance data based on workflow provenance. Compared to manually retrieving the data that our tool gathers, our solution is considerably more efficient.

1.1 *What relevant data can we retrieve from workflow provenance?*

The workflow provenance, in our case exported from the Taverna WFMS, contains information on all the processors or steps that were executed in the workflow. In our case we were interested in the properties *name*, *start-time* and *end-time*. In combination with the workflow definition, we were also able to extract the endpoint of the host in cases of RESTful processors.

1.2 *How can we retrieve the needed performance logs?*

We managed to define a monitoring setup that uses well known DevOps technologies to gather and store performance data of Docker containers. The data is stored in a time-series database that can be queried and accessed over HTTP. In our experiment, we deployed this setup and were successfully able to retrieve accurate performance metrics.

1.3 *To what extent can we automate this process?*

The solution architecture we propose requires the workflow data as input. This includes the workflow definition (.t2flow file) and the workflow provenance (.prov.ttl file). These files are parsed, and the relevant hosts are automatically accessed over HTTP to retrieve the needed performance data.

6.1.2 Research Question 2

R2: *How can we provide insight and recommendations based on the performance data that is found?*

H2: *By providing the ability to diagnose the found data using different methods, we can make recommendations to help improve system performance in the future.*

In our architecture, we propose a method for connecting the resulting performance data to a component that provides services for analysis and diagnosing. The output of this component can be used to make improvements in the infrastructure. Furthermore, in the prototype, we implemented various features that help the user get more insight into the correlation between steps in the workflow and changes in the performance.

2.2 *How can we detect parts of the workflow in need of improvement?*

In our architecture, we include the WFEA component, which can accept the gathered performance data and perform some analysis on it. In our prototype, we simulate this with a simple feature that helps the user correlate time-ranges in the workflow to parts of the performance data. However, the analysis performed could be more complex and include sophisticated event correlation algorithms based on specific needs.

2.3 *How will the findings be delivered?*

In our architecture, we made sure the findings will be delivered in a format that is accessible and easy to understand for the user. In our prototype, we implemented this using a GUI that is well-arranged and shows the findings using lists, timelines and visual graphs using colors for different hosts and steps included in the workflow. Furthermore, our architecture assures that all the information presented in the GUI can also be gathered by programmed infrastructure controllers. This could be useful to make automated scaling decisions.

6.1.3 Requirements

1. **The system should be able to scale up to complex workflows consisting of many web-services.**

Since the operations performed by the CWEA are stateless, it is easy to allow horizontal scaling for the retrieval of performance data once there is a high number of requests being made. Also, this makes it easier to manage inputs containing a large number of host machines. In the design of our tool, we used a microservice architecture to support scaling up the components that are under heavy load.

2. **The system should encourage modification for support of different input files, monitoring tools and diagnosis methods.**

The CWEA is comprised of multiple micro-service components working together. The components communicate with each other using REST and are assigned specific tasks. The components are free to be implemented using any technology, as long as the output data is in JSON format. This way, it is easy for future developers to make adjustments to certain components or implement components that support different workflow formats or monitoring data.

3. **The system should aim at delivering its findings to both users and automated controllers.**

In our solution architecture, we implemented features for both users and automated controllers. For the user, we provide a graphical interface used for interacting with our tool. This is also the interaction method we implemented for the prototype of our tool. Furthermore, the CWEA acts as an API that accepts HTTP calls and can be used to execute different functionalities.

4. **The system should deliver its output in an intuitive and comprehensible manner.**

In the implementation of our prototype, we made sure that the user is presented with an intuitive way of going through the results. To do this, we implemented filterable lists, timelines and interactive graphs. Using consistent colors and zooming and highlighting functionality, the user can efficiently inspect the resulting performance data.

6.2 Limits and possible improvements

Our prototype and experiment are still limited. They could be improved based on the following aspects:

- In our system validation, we set up a basic experiment in which we only gathered data from three individually hosted VM's. This gives us limited insight when it comes to complex workflows connecting to larger numbers of machines that may be running in a clustered manner. To accomplish this, we would need to set up a scale up our experiment horizontally to support a higher number of VM's, running both individually and in clusters.
- In our system validation, we only assume the scenario that is dependent on user interaction. A next step would be to implement an experiment in which automated controllers connect to our prototype. Setting up an environment in which multiple controllers simultaneously connect to our prototype (hosted as a service) would give us a good way of benchmarking its performance.
- In our prototype, we did not include a proper implementation of the WFEA component. Instead, we added some basic utilities like the colors and highlighting features, aiding the user in detecting and correlating events in the performance data. In the future, we could include an implementation of the WFEA using some event correlation algorithm.
- In our prototype implementation, we did not focus much on the design of the UI. To improve the UI for the needs of the users, we could interview stakeholders and discover their interests to make a more fitting design.

7 Conclusion

In this work, we have presented an architecture named CWEA that allows researchers and developers of scientific services to gather and visualize the computational performance of scientific workflows. This data contains detailed records of the resource usage and can be analyzed to detect possible bottlenecks related to the research infrastructure. The architecture we propose is designed to comprise microservices, encouraging easy modification to fit different implementations of performance monitoring, data analysis and workflow storage. Furthermore, it makes our solution scalable to support both simple and complex scientific workflows. In our prototype, we demonstrate the desired functionalities by simulating an infrastructure containing RESTful web services deployed on distributed hosts. To do this, we set up a simple experiment consisting of three VMs acting as hosts, running web services that simulate different types of resource usage. These web services were then implemented in a scientific workflow using Apache Taverna. The outputs resulting from the workflow execution were given as input to the CWEA to retrieve and visualize the relevant performance metrics. By doing this, we were able to show the increased efficiency in analyzing performance data that comes with its automated retrieval based on a scientific workflow execution.

8 Future work

Our work provides a foundation in a field that has not yet been thoroughly explored. Future studies can build on our architecture to improve existing features or implement new ones.

As described in previous sections, our proposed architecture is relying on the WFMS to collect provenance data. This means that the workflow execution needs to complete before the CWEA can use the provenance data. However, being able to collect provenance data as each task is completed will significantly benefit our architecture as results would be able to be presented as on the fly. Such an approach requires further investigation on how to use the appropriate APIs from a multiple WFMS or abstract this process by relying on a provenance repository that will be able to collect provenance data as workflow tasks are completed.

Another issue that will require attention in the future is the persistence of the performance data on each VM. It can be the case that as soon as the workflow execution is over or the VM are no longer used and be terminated, causing the loss of all performance data. While the current implementation of the CWEA is static, future studies should focus on including storage services in which previously gathered performance data can be related to a certain workflow definition. The historical data can be used to perform advanced statistical analysis and event correlation algorithms on the workflow execution. Having performance data from many executions can enable the use of advanced statistical and AI algorithms to detect and predict possible workflow execution failures due to errors in the resource infrastructure. These predictions could be used to automate scaling inside large-scale infrastructures.

Another aspect that can be looked at is the possible uses of our architecture in business infrastructures. In many ways, research infrastructures that support scientific workflows are similar to cloud infrastructures used by large-scale business organizations. While the workflow definitions may differ, it could still be useful to tweak our architecture to support other types of workflows and relate them to different performance data. Most cloud providers supply various tools for gathering and analyzing performance metrics in the cloud but are not connecting it to steps or processes executed in workflows.

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